

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH IN ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE UZBEKISTAN EDUCATION SYSTEM AND WORLD EDUCATION

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Abstract. *It is important to support international research methods in teaching processes that can be organized based on today's requirements, because this serves as a basis for students to take their place in international competitions. In this regard, this article talks about the importance of international studies in evaluating the quality of the education system of Uzbekistan and the world education.*

Keywords: *education, international assessment studies, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, EGMA, EGMA, modern programs, quality of education.*

It is known that in the period of changes, the educational system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. Taking this into account, special attention is being paid to strengthening the material and technical base of general education schools and pre-school educational institutions, to creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the young generation to receive comprehensive education. Also, the issue of training personnel for these fields of education, the allocation of special quotas for these fields in the higher education system, and the fact that pedagogic practices are conducted directly in production institutions are proof that many changes are taking place in the higher education system. In particular, PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), which determines the quality, level and level of education in the world, PIRLS (International Study on Reading and Comprehension of the Text), TIMSS (Mathematics and Science Quality Study at School) there are a number of international programs, such as international monitoring), which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries.

PISA (English - Program for International Student Assessment) is a program that assesses the literacy and practical application of knowledge of 15-year-old students in different countries (reading, mathematics, natural sciences). This program is held once in 3 years. In it, the quality of students' knowledge in reading, mathematics and natural sciences is monitored and evaluated in a 1000-point system. It was originally developed in 1997 and was used for the first time in 2000.

PISA is an international program for assessing the achievements of students in the field of education, the test in which evaluates the knowledge of schoolchildren in the world and the ability to apply them in practice. The main goal of the program is to assess the ability of 15-year-old students to use the knowledge and experience they acquire at school in solving various life tasks in social relations and human activities. This test is held once every three years. Only 15-year-old teenagers participate in the test. The PISA program aimed at monitoring the quality of school education is conducted in three main areas: reading, mathematics and social science literacy.

PIRLS - (English - Progress in International Reading Literacy Study - an international study that determines the level of reading and understanding of the text) the purpose of this

international study is to measure the reading and reading of the text of primary school students of countries with different educational systems. is to identify and evaluate the specific characteristics of the educational system that lead to the readiness of students to achieve different levels of achievement.

More than 50 countries are participating in the PIRLS study. The purpose of this international research is to examine the reading and comprehension skills of primary school students in countries with different educational systems, and the factors that contribute to students' achievement in different educational systems. consists of identifying and evaluating specific characteristics. Of course, such research is of great importance for workers in the field of public education, scientists, methodologists, teachers, parents and public representatives.

TIMSS - (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) is an international monitoring of the quality of teaching mathematics and natural sciences at school, organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA). This program will help to compare the level and quality of knowledge acquired by 4th grade students in mathematics and natural sciences and to identify differences in the national education system. The uniqueness of this program is that it takes into account factors related to the educational content of mathematics and natural sciences in schools around the world, the educational process, the facilities of the educational institution, the level of knowledge of teachers, and the family environment of students. also learns. In addition to these, it should be said that TMSS is also widely used in the educational system of the world countries. The TMSS program was organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA), and this study examined the effectiveness of math and social studies among 4th and 8th grade students. determines quality, level, attitude to science, interest. It is held once every 4 years. Similar to the PIRLS study, this study will conduct additional surveys of students, school administrators, and teachers to identify key barriers to learning in science. This makes it possible to compare educational standards and educational efficiency developed in that country with other countries. Until now, according to the results of TMSS research, the educational system of countries such as the USA, Singapore, Hong Kong, the Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia, and the United Kingdom have the highest indicators. It should be noted that in these countries, in order to master high technologies, industrialization and achieve high level of development, special attention is paid to the mastery of specific subjects at a high level. It is established that the number of students in a group or class does not exceed 16 people in the continuous work on z and in the teaching of specific subjects. This experience is also available in the USA, since 1999, taking into account that one teacher is able to educate and educate 16 children during a 40-minute lesson, by the decision of the president, students in groups in educational institutions the number is set at 16.

The EGRA and EGMA studies are science-based models that test reading and literacy skills and identify the most appropriate solutions to diagnose and address systemic gaps in elementary education. In particular, EGRA and EGMA evaluate reading and math skills in primary grades. Based on the results of the evaluation, new curricula, teaching methods and approaches will be adapted for the better performance of the youth of Uzbekistan. These studies are conducted by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). This project is the first component of the agreement on five-year development goals, signed on September 28, 2019 between XTV and USAID for 50 million dollars. U.S. Ambassador to Uzbekistan Daniel Rosenblum said that EGRA

and EGMA are simple, inexpensive, and powerful tools for assessing elementary school students' literacy and math skills. This tool does not test a child's knowledge, a teacher's teaching or a principal's school management skills.

Our country is taking a worthy place among the developed countries striving for a great future. The use of various programs and technologies in order to improve and increase the efficiency of the education of the growing generation, as well as to teach students to think independently and freely, is becoming a need of the times. Especially in primary education, taking into account the age characteristics of the student, it is appropriate to use various modern and international programs. Using methods that teach students to think independently, develop their creative thinking, and provide them with in-depth knowledge of the basics of science is one of the main tasks of primary education today. In order to implement these tasks, as well as using educational technologies, various methods, methods and handouts in the organization of students' creative work in elementary school classes; they provide information about the EGMA and EGMA programs and use them in the course of the lesson. Learning also plays an important role in the development and maturation of primary school students and the formation of independent thinking skills.

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